

**PERCEIVED IMPACT OF TEACHERS' COMPETENCE ON STUDENTS' SKILLS ACQUISITION
AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN ELECTRONICS WORKS IN SCIENCE AND TECHNICAL
COLLEGES OF KANO STATE**

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the perceived impact of technical teachers' competence on students' skills acquisition and academic achievement in electronics works (EW) in science and technical college Kano State. Two research questions were answered and Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test the two null hypotheses that was formulated to guide the study. The study adopted correlation research design. The population of the study was 72 respondents, there were 15 administrators and 57 teachers of Electronic Works. There was no sampling technique as the entire population was used for the study. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled: Teachers Competency Questionnaire (TCQ). The instrument was validated by three experts from the Department of Electrical Technology Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola. The validated instrument was tested for internal consistency using Cronbach Alpha and a reliability index of 0.81 was obtained. The data collected was analysed using mean and standard deviation statistics and PPMC was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study revealed that there was high effect in teachers' competences on subject matter in teaching electronics works in Science and Technical College, Kano State. Furthermore, the study revealed that teachers' pedagogical competences impact on students' skills acquisition and academic achievements in Electronic Works in Science and Technical College, Kano State. The study recommended that, the ministry of Education should apply the method of examining newly employed teachers or testing their capability on the field of subject matter competences before giving employment, among others.

Keywords: Teachers Competence, Skills Acquisition, Student Achievement, Electronics Works

Introduction

The place of skills acquisition in technical education especially, on the Technical College level cannot be over-emphasized and to achieve this objective, different skills related trades are taught in technical colleges that enhanced students to be self-reliant after graduation. Electronics works trade is one of the trades offered in technical colleges. In Technical Colleges, the curriculum of each trade including Electronic works is broadly divided into three components: General education which accounts for 30% of the total hours required for the program; Trade theory, trade practice and related studies which account for 65%; and Supervised Industrial Training/work experience which accounts for about 5% of the total hours required for the program. The trade practice and supervised industrial training/work experience in the curriculum require laboratory or workshop exercises and practices for the practical part of the training to be acquired by the students. National Business for Technical Examination Board (NABTEB, 2013).

Electronics works involves the maintenance, adjustment, inspecting, installing and repairs of Radio, Television and Electronics circuit (Okolocha & Baba, 2016). According to National Board for Technical Education (NBTE, 2013), the trade is offered at two levels leading to the award of national technical certificate (NTC) for craftsmen and advanced national technical certificate (ANTC) for master craftsmen. The course module for electronic works at the NTC level are: CTD 14: Electrical/Electronic Drawing, CRT 12: Electronics Devices and Circuit, CRT 14: Radio and Audio Frequency Amplifier CRT 15: Satellite Transmission and Reception, CRT 16: Television.

The strength of any educational program largely depends upon the quality of teachers. According to Ajani (2022), the quality of teachers determines the quality education of the citizenry. According to Asiyai (2022), teachers are professionally trained and certificated to manage and control instructional process in the school. For effective teaching and learning activities to take place, a teacher must prepare lesson plans, produces instructional materials and adopts appropriate teaching strategies to achieve instructional objectives. For effective learning, a teacher needs to be equipped with all these skills and attitudes by which he can help his students to learn. In addition to the academic qualification obtained by the teachers, his professional competence is predicated on his pedagogical knowledge, competence subject matter knowledge, communication skills, experiences and technical skills among others.

A skill can be defined as the ability to do something which is acquired by training, while acquisition is the gaining of something for one self (Webster, 1995). Skill acquisition therefore is the ability of an individual acquired through training which enable the individual to effectively carry out a function for the benefit of self and mankind. Skills acquisition is the ability to learn or acquire skills. It involves the development of a new skill, practice of a way of doing things usually gained through training or experience. Isaac, Garba and Falama (2022) viewed skill acquisition as a means of providing an opportunity for people to make the maximum contribution to their own development and to the self-sustaining development of their communities. It is therefore glaring that the need to provide skills is very crucial and vital if effective teaching is to be undertaken by the teacher in the classroom and workshop.

The teaching effectiveness of any teacher is predicated on the acquisition of core skills or competences by the teacher. For quality teaching aimed at sound and balanced education of learner for useful living within the society, such skills should spread through the cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains. According to Asiyai (2008), teaching skills are the specific teacher behaviour systematically designed to help the classroom instruction become effective and meaningful in the teaching and learning process.

Students' achievement can be affected either positively or negatively by the school environment. The role of school is very important in the performance of teachers and students. Teachers are the basic element that greatly influence the teaching learning environment through their abilities, potentialities and professional competence. Only the competent teachers are responsible to bring in the desired changes among their students (Tope, 2012). Teacher's competency enhances a teacher's ability to create an environment that is fair, understanding, and accepting of diverse students, ideas, experiences, and backgrounds. Teachers have been found to be the single most important factor influencing students' skill acquisition and academic achievement.

Teacher competence for improvement purposes is linked to ongoing professional learning and development to improve teaching and learning linked with a set of professional standards. According to Ajani (2022), education can be greatly improved by improving the competence of teachers. Competent teachers appear to be effective with students of all achievement levels, regardless of the individual differences in their classrooms. Teacher competence is an intellectual potency

that exist in teacher's mind and which is realized in doing his/her job according to professional standards. Okwelle & Ebikeseye (2022) indicates that teacher competence refers to the ability of teacher to use professional standards efficiently to help, guide and counsel his/her students so that they can get good achievement.

The teacher's competencies in the areas of teacher's subject matter, pedagogy, communication competencies, teacher's educational qualifications, experience as well as teacher in-service training helps the teacher to be effective in the classroom. Subject matter as an essential component of a teacher's knowledge is neither a new nor a controversial assertion. After all, if teaching entails helping others to learn, then understanding what is to be taught is a central requirement of teaching. As Buchmann (2014) points out that it would be odd to expect a teacher to plan a lesson and evaluate students' assignments if that teacher is ignorant of the learning modules and does not understand the assignment given to the students thereby making the pedagogy difficult for the teacher.

Pedagogical Competencies are different ways usually employed by the teachers or trainers to impart planned lessons to learners. Any selected Pedagogical skill must match the contents or curriculum to be taught in order to achieve stated objectives. There are many Pedagogical skills used by the teachers nowadays. Some are more efficacious than others. Their characteristics, however, vary. In a strict sense, some techniques are more suitable for teaching certain contents, that is, knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes through effective communication (Onabanjo, 2020).

Statement of the Problem

Science and Technical Schools Board, Kano State NABTEB Electronics Works Trade (EWT) result released 2020. Shows That the General Academic Performance of students in Electronics Works Trade (EW) in Technical Colleges in Kano State has decline greatly from 86.7% pass grade to 43.2% pass grade (Science and Technical Schools Board Kano State NABTEB 2020) This decline in academic performance was conveyed by Science and Technical Schools Boards Kano State as result released by NABTEB 2020. The decline in academic performance of student may be as the result of unconnected with unqualified and unprofessional teachers in maintaining, services and repair types of electronic devices, equipment, and appliances such as Computer, radio, and television (Onweh, 2013). The problem of this study is to determine whether competencies possessed by teacher's impact on students' academic achievement. It is against this backdrop that this study seeks to determine the perceived impact of technical teachers' competence on students' skills acquisition and academic achievement in Electronics work in Science and Technical College, Kano State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the perceived impact of technical teachers' competence on students' skill acquisition and academic achievement in Electronic Works in Science and Technical College, Kano State. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Determine the perceived impact of technical teacher's subject matter competences on students' skill acquisition and academic achievement in Electronics Works in Science and Technical College, in Kano State.
2. Determine the perceived impact of technical teacher's pedagogical competences on students' skill acquisition and academic achievement in Electronics Works in Science and Technical College, in Kano State.

Research Questions

The following questions formulated guided the study:

1. What is the perceived impact of technical teacher's subject matter competences on students' skill acquisition and academic achievement in Electronics works in Science and Technical College in Kano State?
2. What is the perceived impact of technical teacher's pedagogical competences on students' skill acquisition and academic achievement in Electronics works in Science and Technical College in Kano State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

HO₁: There is no significant relationship in the mean responses of technical teachers and administrators on the perceived impact of technical teacher's subject matter competences on students' skill acquisition and academic achievement in Electronics works in Science and Technical College, Kano State.

HO₂: There is no significant relationship in the mean responses of technical teachers and administrators on the perceived impact of technical teacher's pedagogical competences on students' skill acquisition and academic achievement in Electronics works in Science and Technical College, Kano State.

Methodology

The research design that was adopted is a correlational research design and was carried out in Kano State which is located in North-West geopolitical zone of Nigeria. Kano State is boarders with Katsina State by the North-West, Jigawa State by East, Bauchi and Kaduna states at the South. It is located between longitude 11°30 and 8°30'E and latitude 11.5°N 8.5°E (Wawo, 2021). The population of the study was 72 respondents, there was 15 administrators and 57 teachers of Electronic Works. There was no sampling technique as the entire population was used for the study. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled: Teachers' Competency Questionnaire (TCQ). The instrument was validated by three experts from the Department of Electrical Technology Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola. The validated instrument was tested for internal consistency using Cronbach Alpha and a reliability index of 0.81 was obtained after a trial test of the instrument on 6 administrators and 10 Electronics works trade teachers in Government Technical College Ringim and Government Technical College Hadejia, both in Jigawa State. Data obtained for this study was analysed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 26.0. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test the null hypotheses, at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule for the research questions was such that when the mean value of an item is 3.50 and above, such an item is considered as "high impact" while items with mean value of 3.49 and below were considered as "low impact". In deciding for the null hypotheses, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient r was interpreted as low, high, or negative, alongside the p -value taking into cognizance the level of significance which is 0.05.

Results

Research Question One

What is the perceived level of impact of technical teacher's subject matter competences on students' skills acquisition and academic achievement in Electronics Works in Science and Technical College, Kano State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Administrators` and Teachers` on Perceived level of subject matter competences

	ITEM STATEMENT	X_A	SD_A	X_T	SD_T	X_{AV}	REMARKS
1	Carry out an experiment to measure current/voltage drops in dc circuits using Avometer.	4.06	1.09	3.77	0.86	3.92	High Impact
2	Demonstrate the effect of load on the output characteristics of PN diodes	3.53	0.83	3.63	0.69	3.58	High Impact
3	Demonstrate how current flows in semiconductor diodes	3.80	0.68	3.68	0.90	3.74	High Impact
4	Perform an experiment to show how to bias a Bipolar Junction Transistor	3.67	0.72	3.56	0.98	3.62	High Impact
5	Demonstrate how to use oscilloscope to measure frequency	3.53	1.06	3.61	1.09	3.57	High Impact
6	Demonstrate a mplitude modulation using modulator kit	3.40	1.06	3.14	0.95	3.27	Low Impact
7	Demonstrate frequency modulation using modulator kit	3.67	0.98	3.14	0.98	3.40	Low Impact
8	Carry out an experiment to measure the frequency of an oscillator.	3.87	0.64	3.59	1.02	3.73	High Impact
9	Construct a dish antenna using locally available materials	3.93	0.79	3.12	1.14	3.53	High Impact
10	Carry out an installation of satellite dish	3.87	0.99	3.02	1.29	3.44	Low Impact
11	Carry out an experiment to show the effect of the internal resistance of an output voltage	3.40	0.74	2.95	1.03	3.18	Low Impact
12	Demonstrate how to determine capacitance of a capacitor using colour codes e.g. red, yellow and black.	3.60	0.63	3.25	0.93	3.43	Low Impact
13	Demonstrate how to determine the tolerance of a resistor from their colour codes	3.67	0.62	3.09	0.76	3.38	Low Impact
14	Carry out an experiment to show the voltage and current relationship in R-L-C circuit	3.20	0.56	3.29	1.18	3.24	Low Impact
	Demonstrate the laws of electrolysis through experiment	3.80	0.77	3.54	1.02	3.67	High Impact
16	Demonstrate how to rewind a radio transformer	3.53	0.92	3.12	1.02	3.32	Low Impact
17	Demonstrate how to use measuring tools (Such as ammeter, voltmeter, etc.).	4.13	0.92	3.63	0.84	3.88	High Impact
18	Carryout the maintenance of the electronic components (such as resistor, diode etc.)	4.07	0.79	3.21	0.79	3.64	High Impact
19	Carry out an experiment on electronic dc circuits e.g solar system	3.33	0.98	3.11	1.05	3.22	Low Impact
20	Demonstrate how to draw electronic symbol such as resistor, diode, and transistor.	3.40	1.12	3.11	1.03	3.26	Low Impact
21	Ability to explain workshop safety rules and their application in electronic workshop	3.80	1.01	3.46	1.07	3.63	High Impact
22	Ability to explain how to select common measuring tools in electronic	4.07	0.88	3.18	0.98	3.62	High Impact
23	Ability to explain how to select and use common electronic tools	3.93	0.96	3.12	1.02	3.52	High Impact
24	Ability to explain how to select and use common electronic gadget	3.87	1.12	3.25	0.83	3.56	High Impact

25	Ability to explain the basic working principles of electronic measuring instrument	3.27	1.44	3.18	1.15	3.23	Low Impact
26	Ability to possess rudimental knowledge and skills of the subject area	4.20	0.68	3.80	0.99	4.00	High Impact
27	Ability to carry out maintenance on electronic battery cells	4.07	0.70	3.49	0.93	3.78	High Impact
28	Demonstrate how to verify the total current flowing in a battery cell	4.07	0.79	3.49	0.85	3.78	High Impact
29	Demonstrate how to measure the total emf of a battery cell	3.67	0.49	3.14	0.89	3.41	Low Impact
30	Carry out an experiment to demonstrate Kirchoff's Law current	3.00	0.93	3.25	1.04	3.13	Low Impact
31	Demonstrate how to install power system to a television circuit	3.20	1.32	3.23	1.07	3.22	Low Impact
32	Explain with simple block diagram function(s) of a television transmitter	3.73	0.88	3.37	1.13	3.55	High Impact
33	Ability to explain how to monitor various devices in electronics	3.53	0.64	3.44	1.12	3.49	Low Impact
34	Ability to demonstrates and apply various components in electronics mother board	3.60	0.74	3.39	1.09	3.50	High Impact
35	Demonstrate how to explain different circuit in electronic	3.73	0.70	3.30	0.98	3.51	High Impact
36	Demonstrate the laws of magnetism through experiment	3.67	0.89	3.19	0.97	3.43	Low Impact
37	Demonstrate how to select electronic tools for a proper project	3.73	0.96	3.39	0.88	3.56	High Impact
38	Demonstrate how to carry out computer maintenance using electronic equipment	3.80	0.94	3.05	0.89	3.42	Low Impact
39	Demonstrate how to measure voltage tolerance in a circuit	3.67	0.72	3.12	0.93	3.40	Low Impact
40	Carry out an experiment to demonstrate ohm`s Law	3.73	1.03	3.49	0.98	3.61	High Impact
Grand Mean		3.70		3.32		3.51	High Impact

X_A = Mean Administrator, SD_A = Standard deviation Administrator, X_T = Mean Teacher, SD_T = Standard deviation Teacher, X_{AV} = Average mean, $N=72$ respondent, $n_A = 15$, $n_T = 57$

Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation of administrators and teachers on the perceived impact of subject matter competences of teachers on students' achievement. The administrators had mean values ranging from 3.00 to 4.20 the administrators mean value is at low impact while the mean value of teachers is greater than the decision level of 3.50. Therefore, administrators rated the subject matter competences of teachers have high impact on students' academic achievement. Similarly, the deviation from the mean ranged from 0.68 to 0.93. The values of deviation from the mean show that there was homogeneity in the responses. On the same Table 1, teachers rated the items have high impact except item number 11 on teachers' subject matter competences on students' achievement with mean values which ranged from 2.95 to 3.80 and the standard deviation range between 0.99 and 1.03 indicate the closeness in the ratings of teachers. The grand mean of 3.70, 3.32 and 3.51 which is above the decision level of 3.50 indicated that teachers' subject matter competency in teaching electronics works have high impact on students' academic achievements in electronics works in science and technical college, Kano State.

Research question 2

What is the perceived level of impact of technical teacher’s pedagogical competences on students’ skills acquisition and academic achievement in Electronics Works in Science and Technical College, Kano State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Administrators` and Teachers` on perceived level of pedagogical competences

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	X_A	SD_A	X_T	SD_T	X_{AV}	RMK
1	Ability of teachers in managing learning program	4.13	0.64	3.93	0.96	4.03	High Impact
2	Ability to interact and control the learning process	3.92	0.70	3.63	1.06	3.78	High Impact
3	Ability to perform an assessment on Electronic Works practical exercises	3.87	0.74	3.47	1.12	3.67	High Impact
4	Ability to explain concept using Collaborative teaching method	3.47	0.74	3.02	0.94	3.25	Low Impact
5	Ability to explain concepts using Coaching teaching method	3.27	0.88	3.09	1.12	3.18	Low Impact
6	Ability to explain concepts using Questioning teaching method	3.47	0.83	3.28	1.19	3.38	Low Impact
7	Ability to explain concepts using Project teaching method	3.73	0.79	3.25	1.06	3.50	High Impact
8	Ability to explain concepts in electronic works using Field Trip teaching method	3.60	0.99	3.25	1.12	3.43	Low Impact
9	Ability to explain concepts in electronic works using Demonstration teaching method	3.87	0.83	3.33	1.19	3.60	High Impact
10	Ability to explain concepts in Electronic Works using Guided Discovery teaching method	3.60	0.82	2.96	1.34	3.28	Low Impact
11	Ability to explain concepts in Electronic Works using Dialogue teaching method	3.67	0.98	2.88	1.09	3.28	Low Impact
12	Ability to explain concepts in Electronic Works using Lecture teaching method	4.27	0.46	3.09	0.93	3.68	High Impact
Grand Mean		3.74		3.27		3.50	High Impact

X_A = Mean Administrator, SD_A = Standard deviation Administrator, X_T = Mean Teacher, SD_T =Standard deviation Teacher, X_{AV} = Average mean, $N=72$ respondent, $n_A =15$, $n_T=57$

Table 2 also shows the mean and standard deviation of administrators and teachers on the perceived impact of pedagogical competences of teachers on students’ academic achievement. The administrators had mean values ranging from 3.27 to 4.27 which is also greater than the decision level of 3.50. Therefore, administrators rated the teachers` pedagogical competency of teachers have high impact on students` academic achievements. Similarly, the deviation from the mean ranged from 0.46 and 0.88. The values of deviation from the mean shows that there was homogeneity in the responses. On the same Table 2, teachers` rated all the items have high impact except items number 10 and 11 on teachers’ pedagogical competences on students` achievement with mean values which ranged from 2.88 to 3.93 and the standard deviation range between 0.96 and 1.09 indicate the closeness in the ratings of teachers. The grand mean of 3.74, 3.27, and 3.50 which is the same with the decision level of 3.50 indicated that teachers` pedagogical competencies in teaching electronics works have high impact on students’ academic achievements in electronics works in science and technical college, Kano State.

Hypothesis One: Perceived impact of technical teachers’ subject matter competences on students’ skills acquisition and academic achievement in Electronics works in Science and Technical College, Kano State.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient between administrators and teachers on teachers’ subject matter competences

GROUPS	N	X	SD	df	r cal	p value	Remark
Administrators	15	3.70	0.28	70	0.38	0.017	Low Correlation
Teachers	57	3.32	0.23				

Coefficient is significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed). N=Number of respondent SD=standard deviation X=Mean

Table 3 revealed that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient r was given as 0.38 which given as low and positive. Therefore, there is a low and positive correlation between the mean response of administrators and teachers. The mean of administrators is 3.70 and the teachers have a mean of 3.32 which also is a pointer to the relationship as indicated by the Pearson Correlation Coefficient. Since the p-value of 0.017 is lower than 0.05 level of significance, this implies that there is low but positive correlation between administrators and teachers on the perceived impact of teachers’ subject matter competency on students’ skills acquisition and academic achievements in Electronics Works in Science and Technical College, Kano State.

Hypothesis Two: The perceived impact of technical teacher’s pedagogical competences on students’ skills acquisition and academic achievements in Electronics works in Science and Technical College, Kano State.

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient between administrators and teachers on teachers’ pedagogical competences

GROUPS	N	X	SD	Df	r cal	p value	Remark
Administrators	15	3.74	0.25	70	0.58	0.060	High Correlation
Teachers	57	3.27	0.31				

Coefficient is significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed). N=Number of respondent SD=standard deviation X=Mean

Table 4 revealed that there is a positive correlation between the administrators and the teachers the table revealed that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient r is given as 0.58 which is positive and high. Similarly, the mean rating of administrators is 3.74 and that of the teachers mean is 3.27 which is also a pointer to the relationship as indicated by the Pearson Correlation Coefficient. Since, the p-value of .060 is greater than 0.05 level of significance this implies that there is high but positive correlation between administrators and teachers on the perceived level of impact of teachers’ pedagogical competences on students’ skills acquisition and academic achievements in Electronics Works in Science and Technical College, Kano State.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of the study revealed that teachers' subject matter competences in teaching electronics works has effect on students' skills acquisition and academic achievements. Furthermore, the corresponding null hypotheses revealed a low but positive correlation coefficient between mean response of administrators and teachers in Science and Technical College in Kano State. This finding was in agreement with the findings of Obot (2014) who Conducted a study on students' perception of the teachers' competence in subject matter on students' interest in learning social studies Education. The research on Influence of Teachers' Competence in Subject Matter on students' interest in the learning of Social Studies Education, was aimed at determining the contribution of students' perception of teachers' competence in subject matter on students' interest in learning with particular attention to Social Studies Education. The findings also is in agreement with the findings of Arzi and White (2007) who conducted a study on teachers upheld the change in teachers' knowledge of subject matter: It followed secondary school science teachers, through sequences of individual interviews in which change in content knowledge was probed via concept profiles – a word-association method.

The findings revealed that the teachers' pedagogical competences for teaching Electronics works effect on students' skills acquisition and academic achievements. Furthermore, the corresponding null hypotheses, revealed a high but positive correlation coefficient between the mean response of administrators and teachers in Science and Technical College in Kano State. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Filgona, Sakiyo and Gwany (2020) whom conducted their studies on teachers' pedagogical content knowledge and students' academic achievement.

Conclusion

The study concluded that the findings of the research questions revealed that the teachers' subject matter competences in teaching electronics works has effect on students' skills acquisition and academic achievements, the teacher has mastered the content and effect on students. The teacher employed different teaching skills, knowledge, methods on the pedagogical competences on students' skills acquisition.

Recommendation

1. The Ministry of Education should apply the method of examining newly employed teachers or testing their capability on the field of subject matter competences before giving employment.
2. Government should test teachers' pedagogical approaches in teaching methods, only those recommended teachers be giving employment, in the ministry of education Kano State

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